

Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part II.

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In a system containing a conjugated double bond of the type

$O=C-C=CR$, the ethylenic linkage is generally found to be more active than the carbonyl (Harries and Lellmann, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 230, 2726; Harries and Jablonski, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 1371; Vorlander, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2053; *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 273; Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1214; Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4464; Sen Gupta, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347). To ascertain the position of the ethylenic bond is thus a matter of considerable importance in determining the constitution of synthetic products derived from such systems, three types which may be cited for our present purpose :

These represent benzylidene acetone, hydroxymethylene ketone and acetyl acetone respectively. It is usually found that in the first case the ethylenic linkage is more reactive than the carbonyl. Thus in the reduction of unsaturated ketones of the general formula, $R_2C=CH \cdot CO \cdot R$, the ethylenic linkage is the one which is primarily attacked whilst the carbonyl group is affected only secondarily (*cf.* Harries, *loc. cit.*). The same is true of the addition of hydroxylamine, ammonia (Koehl and Dinter, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 172), hydrogen cyanide, etc. (*cf.* Lapworth, *loc. cit.*). Vorlander (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2053) has shown that the ethylenic linkage alone is involved in the reaction between sodium malonic ester and derivatives of cinnamic acid, $C_6H_5 \cdot CH=CH \cdot CO \cdot X$, where X represents any group. There are, however, examples which do not support this view, such as the reduction of cinnamyl formic acid to phenyl-hydroxyisocrotonic acid (Erlenmeyer, jun., *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2529; 1904, 37, 1318), and the addition of hydrogen cyanide and magnesium methyl iodide to the carbonyl group of cinnamic aldehyde (Kohler,

Amer. Chem. J., 1904, **31**, 642 ; 1905, **33**, 153, 333 ; 1907, **36**, 529). Like most chemical hypotheses, therefore, the principle that in a conjugated double bonded system the ethylenic linkage is more reactive, requires to be critically examined before the few exceptions like those mentioned above could be regarded as arguments against it.

In a system of the second type, as shown by one of us (Sen Gupta, *loc. cit.*), the ethylenic linkage is far more reactive than the carbonyl. Thus the condensation of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone and cyanacetamide leads to the formation of quinoline and not isoquinoline derivatives, as proved definitely by the isolation of pure quinoline by zinc dust distillation.

Arguments may be put forward against this conception on the ground that hydroxymethylene ketones are also capable of existing in the keto-aldehyde phase and that the formyl group which is thus produced in the molecule, being more reactive than the ketone, gives rise to the same set of products as demanded by the superior reactivity of the ethylenic linkage. But since the identical quinoline derivative was obtained by condensing either hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone or its acetate,

with cyanacetamide, the main theorem that the ethylenic linkage in a conjugated system is more reactive than the ketonic group, is not affected thereby.

Quite different is the case with 1:3-carbonyl compounds, for, like the unsaturated type (I) or hydroxymethylene ketones (type II), they do not possess any ethylenic bond in themselves as represented in the ordinary structural formulae. It is only when they tautomerise to their enolic modifications, that conjugated double bonds of the same type as in (I) and (II) are set up. The question now arises whether in reacting with such compounds, the ethylenic linkage formed is responsible for the initial condensation or the

carbonyl group, remaining as such, becomes the centre of reaction? A suitable reagent to test this point is found in cyanacetamide where the methylene group is readily reactive. The point here is whether the addition of the methylene group takes place at the double bond, or it reacts with the carbonyl group with the elimination of water.

In the literature which has special reference to the chemistry and condensation of β -diketones (or β -ketoic esters), the work of Moir (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 100) and that of Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1022) are noteworthy. The former is significant from the fact that Moir thoroughly investigated the compound obtained by condensing acetyl acetone with ethyl cyanacetate in the presence of an excess of ammonia, and claims to have established the mechanism of all such reactions. According to him, the first part of the reaction involves the formation of cyanacetamide and acetyl acetonamine which then react with each other to give the closed ring system as shown below:—

Moir preferred this mechanism owing to the reason that on heating acetylacetonamine with cyanacetmethylamide, the sole product of the reaction was the *N*-methyl derivative of (IV). But the reaction is quite as readily explained by applying the general theorem upheld in this investigation:

If Moir's explanation were general, the condensation of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone with cyanacetamide should yield an

isoquinoline derivative, whereas this is not the case. Moreover, identical products are obtained whether one condenses hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* with cyanacetic ester in alcoholic ammonia, or the amide of hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* with ethyl cyanacetate in presence of diethylamine or piperidine (Sen Gupta, *loc. cit.*, p. 1355).

The next point to be considered is, Which of the carbonyl groups enolises in the case of a β -diketone? If symmetrical groupings be present in the molecule such as in acetyl acetone, the question does not arise. The case of unsymmetrical β -diketones, such as benzoyl acetone, has been thoroughly investigated by Bardhan (Thesis for the D.Sc. Degree of the University of Calcutta. 1924), who finds that the negative nature of the group favours enolisation which determines the more reactive centre of condensation. Whether the presence of one of the ketonic groups in a cyclic compound influences its activity was necessarily considered to be of importance in establishing the general character of Bardhan's hypothesis. As already mentioned (*loc. cit.*) if the enolisation is not exclusively limited to one particular ketonic group, there would be isomeric condensation products possible. Accordingly acetyl *cyclohexanones* were taken and the course of their reaction with cyanacetamide was studied in the presence of Knoevenagel's as well as Michael's reagent, with a view further to examine the directive influence of these condensing agents.

The experimental evidence so far shows that acetyl *cyclohexanone* and cyanacetamide condense to give rise to a mixture of quinoline and isoquinoline derivatives, thus indicating that the reduced cyclic residue has no special directive influence on the enolisation. But that the enolisation of a carbonyl group is at the bottom of such reactions is proved by a significant negative result obtained in the course of this investigation on attempting to condense 2-acetyl-2-methyl-*cyclohexanone*-1 with cyanacetamide in presence of piperidine. No condensation product could be readily obtained, but on keeping the reaction mixture overnight, a very small quantity of a substance was isolated which on methylation melted at a temperature almost identical with the melting point of the compound obtained by methylating the condensation product of acetyl-*cyclohexanone* and cyanacetamide. There was no doubt that in the experiment recorded acetyl-*cyclohexanone* was methylated, as by heating the methylated acetyl-*cyclohexanone* with potash, *o*-methyl-*cyclohexanone* was obtained (*vide* Experimental part). The removal, therefore, of *o*

the labile hydrogen atom necessary for the enolisation of the ketonic group had rendered such condensations impossible or at least very difficult (*cf.* Rogerson and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1685; Haworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 480). The small quantity of product that separated could have thus been possible from any the least quantity of acetyl-*cyclohexanone* escaping methylation. Of far reaching consequence is the interpretation of this negative result, as it further disproves the ordinarily accepted mechanism of Knoevenagel's reaction (*cf.* Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 329).

It is next of importance to decide as to which of the two groups, methylene (CH_2) or the amido of cyanacetamide takes the precedence in the addition to the enolised double bond. As the electropositive character of the admic hydrogen is far less than that of the methylene hydrogen of cyanacetamide, it is highly improbable that the former should add on to the double bond in preference to the latter. Besides the production of quinoline derivatives in the condensation of hydroxymethylene ketones with cyanacetamide (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347) definitely establishes the greater affinity of the methylene group for the double bond in a conjugated system. This fact goes directly against Moir's hypothesis. It should be mentioned in this connection that Moir's preference to his own mechanism of reaction was greatly actuated by his supposed difficulty of eliminating a molecule of water for the closure of ring when alkyl substituted amides were taken. That this difficulty is imaginary was shown by our method of representing such reaction (*loc. cit.*). He had not also thought of the other contingency, namely, substitution of a methylene hydrogen atom of cyanacetamide by alkyl. This we have done and found that acetyl-*cyclohexanone* and methylcyanacetamide, $\text{CN}.\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3).\text{C}(\text{O}).\text{NH}_2$ yield the same product as the one from acetyl-*cyclohexanone* and cyanacetamide itself, eliminating thus not two molecules of water, but one molecule of water and one molecule of methyl alcohol:

This again points to the correctness of our view that in a conjugated double bonded system, the ethylenic linkage is more

reactive than the carbonyl, particularly in respect to cyanacetamide and similar substances. Expressed otherwise, in β -diketones even the ketonic group acts through setting up of ethylenic linkage. It is in the light of these experiments that Moir's explanation of the mechanism of reaction between cyanacetamide and acetylacetone is discarded, as, according to him, there is no provision for the enolisation of the ketonic group before its reaction with the methylene group of cyanacetamide.

When acetyl *cyclohexanone* is condensed with cyanacetamide in aqueous—alcoholic solution in the presence of piperidine, a product is obtained, which dissolves in alkali forming a colourless solution from which it is precipitated unchanged by the addition of acid. On hydrolysing the substance with fuming hydrochloric acid, the cyanogen group is eliminated. From the solubility or from any other property of the hydrolysed product, it is not possible to determine whether the condensation product is a mixture or a single substance.

The reasons which have led to the conclusion that the condensation product is a mixture of quinoline and *isoquinoline* derivatives are as follows.

(1) On hydrolysing the condensation product, the cyanogen group is split off. The product may be a mixture of

or one of these. The hydrolysed product (having the benzene ring fully reduced) yielded, on distillation with zinc dust in a current of hydrogen at a low red heat, a heavy liquid of quinoline like odour. On redistilling the mixture over heated litharge, a purer liquid of quinoline like smell and colour boiling at 239° was obtained. This gave a picrate having a melting point lower than that of γ -methyl quinoline or α -methyl*isoquinoline*. Similarly, a methiodide well crystallisable but of an indifferent melting point was obtained.

(2) The condensation product gave a methyl ether which, after fractional crystallisation, yielded different crops having different melting points but the same percentage composition. This is only possible if the mother substance be a mixture of two isomers.

(3) The hydrolysed products have no sharp melting points.

If now the condensation product obtained from acetyl*cyclohexanone* and cyanacetamide be regarded as mixtures it is clear that by

fixing the enolising carbon atom one should get either a quinoline or an isoquinoline derivative. Accordingly ethyl *cyclohexanone* carboxylate was taken as a suitable reagent for testing this view. The labile hydrogen in the carboxylate can only enolise the ketonic oxygen and as such the reaction with cyanacetamide whether in the presence of sodium ethoxide or piperidine, should be represented as below.

The product obtained in this way corresponds to the above composition and melted after crystallisation at 278-280°, shrinking only a few degrees earlier. This characteristic of sharp melting point is absent in similar products obtained from acetyl*cyclohexanone* and cyanacetamide and leads one to regard it as a pure product and not a mixture. It would be important now to resolve this provisionally accepted isoquinoline derivative into simpler products and finally distil it with zinc dust to obtain isoquinoline itself. This will be undertaken as soon as time and opportunity permit.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of 2-Acetylcyclohexanone with Cyanacetamide.

2-Acetyl-*cyclohexanone* was prepared according to Leser's method (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1900, (iii), 23, 370; cf. Borsche, *Annalen*, 1910, 377, 70) and obtained as a colourless liquid boiling at 108-111° under 20 mm. pressure. The yield was about 32 per cent. of the weight of *cyclohexanone* used.

Cyanacetamide (6 g.) was dissolved in water by warming, and 2-acetyl-*cyclohexanone* (10 g.) added, with just enough alcohol to effect the solution. About one c.c. of piperidine being added, the solution was then warmed up to 60° when after 3 or 4 minutes crystals began to separate. The flask was then kept for a while at a temperature of about 40°, when its contents set to a crystalline solid. The flask was loosely corked and left overnight at the room temperature. Next day the condensation product (about 11 g.) was collected. The mother-liquor, on evaporation, gave about 1.5 g. more of it.

The condensation product was moderately soluble in boiling glacial acetic acid from which it was obtained in colourless prismatic needles, darkening at 280°, and beginning to decompose at about

290°. This compound was already described by one of us (Sen Gupta, *loc. cit.*), but no further work regarding its constitution was since taken in hand.

The same compound can be obtained by condensing 2-acetyl-cyclohexanone with cyanacetamide in the presence of sodium ethoxide as follows.—Sodium (0.35 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol. An alcoholic solution of cyanacetamide (1.2 g.) was added to the sodium ethoxide solution. To the sodium salt of cyanacetamide thus precipitated, acetyl cyclohexanone (2 g.) was gradually added with shaking. The sodium salt dissolved, and the solution, which assumed a deep yellow colour, was left overnight. Next morning the solution, after being diluted with water, was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when the condensation product (about 2 g.) was obtained. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid with the addition of a few drops of water, the product was obtained in colourless prismatic needles which begin to decompose above 290°. (Found: N, 14.98. $C_{11}H_{13}ON$, requires N, 14.89 per cent.).

These condensation products are insoluble in cold water, very sparingly soluble in boiling water or alcohol. They readily dissolve in alkali to a colourless solution from which they are reprecipitated unchanged by the addition of acid. Concentrated hydrochloric acid dissolves them; from the acid solution they are precipitated on dilution with water. Ferric chloride imparts no colouration to their alcoholic solution.

Hydrolysis of the Condensation Product.—The condensation product (4 g.), obtained by using piperidine as the condensing agent, was heated with fuming hydrochloric acid (28 c. c.) in a sealed tube for four hours at 170°. A substance crystallised in the tube; this was washed carefully and recrystallised from a minimum quantity of water. It was found to be a hydrochloride: it forms colourless needles, sintering at 205° but melting completely at 252°. (Found: N, 6.84; Cl, 17.54. $C_{10}H_{13}ON, HCl$ requires N, 7.01; Cl, 17.79 per cent.).

The substance is soluble in water, reacts acid towards litmus, forms an insoluble silver chloride with silver nitrate solution, and readily decolourises aqueous permanganate. It is also soluble in alcohol to which ferric chloride imparts a deep red colouration. Concentrated hydrochloric acid dissolves it; from the solution it can be reprecipitated on dilution with water. The hydrochloride, when dissolved in boiling water and gradually neutralised with sodium carbonate, yields the hydroxybase which is obtained from alcohol in

colourless needles sintering at 225° and melting at 235°. The compound has no sharp melting point. (Found: N, 8·94. $C_{10}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 8·59 per cent.).

The hydroxybase is less soluble in water. Its aqueous solution is neutral to litmus. It is soluble in alcohol, concentrated hydrochloric acid and alkali. Ferric chloride imparts a deep red colouration to their alcoholic solution.

Reduction of the Hydroxybase.—The hydrolysed product (7 g.) was intimately mixed with zinc dust (50 g.) in an ordinary combustion tube with one of its ends drawn out and bent. The front part of the tube contained a length of about 12 cm. of zinc dust. The distillation was conducted at a low red heat in a current of hydrogen, when ammoniacal vapours began to escape. In course of half an hour about 1·5 g. of a dark yellowish liquid collected. The liquid thus obtained was mixed with litharge in a hard glass tube closed at one end. This was heated to dull redness in a combustion furnace when a reddish yellow liquid having the odour of quinoline distilled over, ammoniacal vapours escaping condensation at the same time. The liquid was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, shaken up with ether to remove any non-basic impurities and reprecipitated by the addition of alkali. The ethereal extract of the base was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled. A clear liquid, which soon turned yellow, was collected at about 239° which gave a picrate melting indifferently between 189° and 194° after crystallisation. Another crop of it was obtained from the mother-liquor which melted at 154°-155° sintering and moistening a few degrees earlier. A methiodide was obtained which also melted indifferently between 174° and 176° and the mother-liquor yielded a product having a melting point of 136°-137°. [Found (for picrate, m.p. 189-94°): N, 14·78; (for picrate, m.p. 154-55°) N, 15·87. Methylquinoline or methyl *iso*quinoline picrate requires N, 15·05 per cent.].

Probably during zinc dust distillation or litharge oxidation the methyl group was partially eliminated yielding quinoline and *iso*quinoline. Quinoline or *iso*quinoline picrate requires N, 15·64 per cent. That both the methyl quinolines are simultaneously formed is proved from the fractional isolation of methyl ethers.

Methyl Ether.—The condensation product (2 g.) obtained from acetyl*cyclohexanone* and cyanacetamide was dissolved in dilute alkali and treated with an excess of dimethyl sulphate. The solution, which became warm, was then gently heated to boiling, maintained alkaline and the precipitate formed collected. When crystallised

from water, the methyl ether had no sharp melting point. Repeated fractional crystallisation from water, however, gave a product which melts at 179°-180°. The mother-liquor yielded two crops, one melting at 175° and the other at 158°, but sintering a few degrees earlier. The mixed m.p. of the first crop melting at 179°-180° with that melting at 158° was 170°-173°. The crop melting at 179°-180° was recrystallised when an ether having m.p. 182°-183° was obtained [Found: N, 14.07 (first crop); N, 13.96 (second crop). $C_{11}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13.87 per cent.]. The two methyl ethers are therefore identical in composition, though isomeric.

Condensation of 6-Methyl-2-acetyl-cyclohexanone and Cyanacetamide.

The acetyl compound was prepared in the usual way from *o*-methylcyclohexanone which yields about 20 per cent. of its weight of 6-methyl-2-acetyl-cyclohexanone as a colourless liquid boiling at 115-120°/25 mm.

The condensation was effected, as usual, by means of piperidine. The condensed product was somewhat more soluble in dilute alcohol than its previous analogue. The yield in this case was about 84 per cent. of the theory. It crystallises from dilute acetic acid in fine prismatic needles, darkening above 250° and finally melting with decomposition at 275°. (Found: N, 14.20. $C_{11}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13.87 per cent.). The substance is soluble in boiling water; it dissolves in alkalis to a colourless solution from which it is partially precipitated unchanged by the addition of acid. No methyl ether was obtained by treating its alkaline solution with dimethyl sulphate.

On hydrolysis with fuming hydrochloric acid, a compound was obtained which was very soluble in concentrated acid. It was isolated by evaporating the acid solution to dryness and extracting the residue with boiling absolute alcohol. On cooling needle-like crystals separated out. Recrystallised from rectified spirit the substance melted at 242-243°. (Found: N, 8.15. $C_{11}H_{16}ON$ requires N, 7.91 per cent.).

The hydrolysed product is not appreciably soluble in water, and silver nitrate solution has no action on it. It possesses a sharp melting point and melts without decomposition. In this respect it differs from any of its other homologues.

Condensation of 5-Methyl-2-acetylcyclohexanone and Cyanacetamide.

The diketone was obtained as a colourless oil. b.p. 128-29°/19

mm. The yield was about 32 per cent. of the weight of *m*-methylcyclohexanone used.

The condensation product was prepared as usual. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid with the addition of a few drops of water, it was obtained in prismatic needles darkening above 260° and showing no sign of melting even at 280°. The yield in this case is almost theoretical. (Found: N, 13·92. $C_{11}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13·87 per cent.).

The compound obtained by hydrolysing the condensation product with fuming hydrochloric acid crystallises from rectified spirit in long needles sintering at 195° and melting at 200-201°. (Found: N, 8·23. $C_{11}H_{14}ON$ requires N, 7·91 per cent.).

Condensation of 4-Methyl-2-acetylcyclohexanone and Cyanacetamide.

p-Methylcyclohexanone yields 20 to 22 per cent. of its weight of acetylcyclohexanone as a colourless liquid distilling between 115° and 120° under 22 mm. pressure.

The condensation was brought about in the usual way. The reaction takes place within 5 or 6 minutes. The yield is about 78 per cent. of the theory. From dilute acetic acid the substance crystallises in beautiful prismatic plates darkening above 270°. (Found: N, 13·97. $C_{11}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13·87 per cent.).

It is soluble in alkali but no methyl ether was obtained by treating the alkaline solution with dimethyl sulphate. Acids liberate the compound unchanged from its solution in alkali.

The hydrolysis of the condensation product was effected as usual by heating it with fuming hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube. The hydrolysed product crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles moistening at 210° and melting at 230°-232°. It is soluble in boiling water but this solution has no action on silver nitrate.

Condensation of 2-Acetylcyclohexanone and Methyl cyanacetamide.—Ethyl methylcyanacetate was prepared from the sodium salt of ethyl cyanacetate and methyl iodide in the usual way. The ester was then treated with strong ammonia. On concentrating the ammoniacal solution and cooling, a solid mass was obtained. This was washed with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Methylcyanacetamide (1·2 g.) was dissolved in water by slightly warming. 2-Acetylcyclohexanone (1·7 g.) was then added with just enough alcohol to effect the solution of the oily diketone. Piperidine was added; the colour of the solution soon deepened.

The flask was then heated up to 65°. An appreciable quantity of a solid separated out after a short time. The flask was left overnight. Next day about 0.8 g. of the condensation product was collected and about 0.2 g. was found in the mother-liquor. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid with a few drops of water, beautiful crystals darkening above 280° were obtained. (Found: N, 14.91. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2$, requires N, 14.89 per cent.). It dissolves in alkali to a colourless solution, from which it is precipitated unchanged by acid. It is insoluble in water and alcohol, soluble in concentrated hydrochloric acid and has properties identical with those of the condensation product obtained from 2-acetyl-cyclohexanone and cynacetamide.

The same condensation product was obtained by condensing 2-acetylcyclohexanone and methylcyanacetamide in presence of sodium ethoxide. It crystallises from glacial acetic acid in beautiful long prismatic needles. (Found: N, 15.24. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2$, requires N, 14.89 per cent.).

Condensation of 2-Methyl-2-acetylcyclohexanone and Cyanacetamide.—2-Methyl-2-acetylcyclohexanone was prepared in the following way:—Sodium salt of 2-acetylcyclohexanone was prepared by adding sodium wire to a benzene solution of the diketone, and finishing the reaction by heating under reflux on a water-bath. The sodium salt was then digested with an excess of methyl iodide in a pressure bottle for 8 hours at 70°. Sodium iodide formed was filtered off at the pump. After removing benzene from the filtrate, the residual liquid was distilled when a colourless liquid (4 g.) boiling at 130-133° under 48 mm. pressure was collected. That it was 2-methyl-2-acetyl-cyclohexanone was proved by hydrolysing it with concentrated alcoholic potash when an oil was obtained, giving a semicarbazone, m.p. 195-196°. A mixture of this semicarbazone with that obtained from *o*-methylcyclohexanone also melted at 196°.

2-Methyl-2-acetylcyclohexanone (3.5 g.) was treated with cyanacetamide (2 g.) in the usual way in the presence of piperidine but no condensation product separated even after 6 hours. The flask was left overnight when on the next morning a minute quantity of a solid was collected, which dissolved in alkali. On treating this solution with dimethyl sulphate, a methyl ether was obtained melting indifferently below 155° after crystallisation from water. The mother-liquor, on dilution and acidification, became fluorescent but no other condensation product was obtained.

Condensation of Ethyl cycloHexanone Carboxylate with Cyanacetamide: Formation of 1: 3: 10-Trioxo-4-cyano-hexahydroisoquinoline ?—The cyclohexanone carboxylate was prepared from cyclohexanone and oxalic ester according to Kötze's method (*Annalen*, 1905, 342, 346). Its condensation with cyanacetamide was effected both by Knoevenagel's as well as by Michael's reaction. But the latter method was found to give a purer product. Cyanacetamide (2 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol by boiling and as crystals began to appear on cooling, sodium (0.55 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol was added. To the sodium salt of cyanacetamide thus precipitated ethyl cyclohexanone carboxylate (4 g.) was gradually added with shaking. Soon a clear solution was obtained; but shortly after the sodium salt had dissolved, a beautiful silky precipitate was found in the flask and within a few minutes a thick sludge was formed. The flask being corked, was left overnight at the room temperature. Next day, water was added to make a complete solution of the sodium salt, which on acidification gave a white precipitate. This was collected and was dissolved in boiling alcohol; from the solution which gradually turned pinkish the expected isoquinoline derivative separated as colourless crystals. The compound in course of time takes a pink tinge by coming in contact with air. Repeated crystallisation shows the same phenomenon. It melts with decomposition at 278-280°, sintering at 273°. [Found: N, 13.73, 13.88. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$, (i.e. the isoquinoline derivative with the aldol phase on) requires N, 13.46 per cent. Most probably a trace of the anhydro base is present which increases the percentage of nitrogen.]

The substance dissolves in alkali to form a colourless solution from which it is precipitated unchanged by acid. Ferric chloride imparts a dark greenish colour to its alcoholic solution. It is provisionally regarded as an isoquinoline derivative (*loc. cit.*).